

MEDICAL SCIENCES

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SELECTION OF TEMPORARY FILLING MATERIALS FOR HIGH-QUALITY SEALING OF THE TOOTH CAVITY

Abstract.

In endodontic treatment, an important task is to ensure the tightness of the obturation along the entire length of the root canal. After filling the canal, regardless of the method, microscopic pores remain and the marginal seal of the seam is broken. All filling materials are usually water-soluble, which leads to micropenetration. Despite a sufficient number of studies on sealing the apical part of the root canal, the problem of reliable sealing of the root canal orifice requires more attention. Due to the loss of dental tissue volume, temporary filling materials are often used to close the dental cavity, but most of them do not provide reliable sealing. The purpose of the study is to evaluate the tightness of various temporary fillers. A study was conducted on the permeability of temporary materials through staining after 7 and 14 days on 30 extracted incisors and canines. The teeth were divided into 3 groups: "Tempofil", "Unifas" and "Ketac molar". As a result, after 7 days, in the first group micropenetration was in 100% of cases, in the second – in 60%, in the third – in 40%.

Key words: *root canal, endodontic treatment, temporary fillings*

When carrying out endodontic treatment, one of the most important tasks is to ensure the tightness of the obturation along the entire length of the root canal from the mouth to its apical part, as well as maintaining the tightness in the long term. As is known, after filling a root canal, regardless of the method used, pores remain at the microscopic level, violations of the marginal seal at the dentin-sealer, sealer-gutta-percha border. In turn, all sealers, without exception, are water-soluble to one degree or another, resulting in micro-seepage. Microleakage through the apical foramen and methods for ensuring the tightness of the apical part of the root canal have been sufficiently studied and published both in foreign literature . [1, 2, 5, 6]. However, in our opinion, a small amount of work has been devoted to the problem of reliable sealing of the tooth cavity (root canal mouth). After endodontic treatment, a large volume of hard tooth tissue is lost and permanent restoration or the manufacture of an orthopedic structure is not always possible. Therefore, for a certain period, the tooth cavity is closed with temporary filling material [3]. According to the literature, the majority of temporary fillings do not provide reliable sealing of the tooth cavity. This is due to the fact that due to prolonged use, under the influence of saliva, the temporary filling dissolves and allows oral fluid to enter the tooth cavity. Consequently, the orifice of an obstructed root canal can become a "gate of entry" for re-infection of the root canal. In the absence of reliable isolation of the tooth cavity, bacterial infection is observed within a period of 20 days to 4 weeks in 50% of cases. Therefore, in order to prevent the penetration of bacteria into the root canal system for the period between patient appointments, a

temporary filling must hermetically seal the tooth cavity [2, 4, 7]. The purpose of the study is to study and give a comparative assessment of the consistency of materials used as temporary fillings after endodontic treatment in relation to sealing the tooth cavity. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were formulated: 1 to conduct a microscopic study of the marginal permeability of materials used as temporary fillings; 1 give a comparative assessment of the sealing of the tooth cavity depending on the type of material. Materials and methods. The quality of sealing of the dental cavity with temporary fillings was studied by assessing their permeability to passive dye after 7 and 14 days. The studies were carried out on 30 incisors and canines of the upper jaw removed according to indications. After mechanical and medicinal treatment, followed by drying, the root canals were filled using the lateral condensation method. The roots of the teeth were then covered with molten wax up to the level of the enamel-cement junction to prevent microleakage through the apex of the tooth. Depending on the type of filling material, the teeth were divided into 3 groups of 10 teeth each. The cavities of the teeth of the first group were filled with dentin paste "Tempofil", for the teeth of the second group they used zinc-phosphate cement "Unifas", for the third group - glass ionomer cement "Ketac molar". The average height of the filling was 4.5 ± 0.1 mm. Next, the teeth were immersed in a vessel with dye (2% aqueous solution of methyl blue) and placed in a thermostat at a temperature of 37 ± 10 C, having previously divided each group into 2 subgroups of 5 teeth each. The first subgroup of teeth was kept in the dye for 7 days, the second for 14 days. At the end of the specified time, in

laboratory conditions, the teeth were dissected in a vertical plane passing through the longitudinal axis of the tooth (Fig. 1). The prepared thin sections from the obtained samples were examined under a Technival stereomicroscope (Carl Zeiss Jena, Germany), (up to x50) and a MeF-3 optical microscope (ReichertJung, Austria), (more than x50). The permeability of the dye was determined as the average value of the data from n experiments using the formula: where L is the average permeability value; Δh_i —staining height of the i -sample, mm; n is the number of samples. Research results. As a result of studying the samples kept in the dye for 7 days, it was revealed that in the teeth of the first group, microleakage of the dye occurred in 100% of cases. The dye penetrated into the structure of the filling throughout its entire thickness, at the filling-tooth border, as well as into the mouth of the root canal to a depth of about 0.5 mm (Fig. 2). Studies of samples from the second group showed that dye penetration was observed in 60% of cases (Fig. 3). In samples of the third group, dye penetration was recorded in 40% of cases (Fig. 4). Zinc phosphate cement “Uniface” and glass ionomer cement “Ketac molar” allowed the dye to penetrate into the tooth canal to varying depths only at the edges of the filling. Studies of teeth that were kept in the dye for 14 days showed the following results. In the samples of the first group, penetration of the dye into the root canal and its distribution along the gutta-percha in the apical direction were observed (Fig. 5). In the second group, complete staining of the root filling to the mouth of the root canal was found in 80% of cases.

In the second group, staining of the root filling was found in 60% of cases. The average dye penetration depths are shown in Fig. 6. The diagram illustrates that

the greatest depth of dye penetration was recorded using Tempofil dentin paste.

Conclusions

1. The best sealing of the tooth cavity and isolation of obstructed root canal mouths is provided by a filling made of glass ionomer cement.

2. The maximum time for using a temporary dentin filling should not exceed 7 days.

3. The thickness of the temporary filling must be at least 5 mm.

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